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REALISATION OF EXISTENTIAL PROCESSES IN EKEGUSII DECLARATIVE CLAUSES

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Abstract: This study investigates the realization of existential processes in Ekegusii declarative clauses within the framework of Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). Drawing on Halliday's (1994) model and its later elaboration by Halliday and Matthiessen (2014), the research situates existential processes as a key component of the ideational metafunction, where language encodes experiences and represents the presence of entities. While transitivity analysis in SFL encompasses six major process types—material, mental, relational, behavioral, verbal, and existential—this study focuses on existential clauses, which assert the occurrence or presence of entities, typically through a single participant, the Existent. Using descriptive analysis, data from Ekegusii were examined to identify how existential processes are structured and expressed in declarative contexts. The findings reveal that Ekegusii employs a range of grammatical and lexical strategies to encode existence, highlighting patterns both unique to the language and comparable to structures in other natural languages. The study contributes to a broader understanding of transitivity in Bantu languages and underscores the significance of existential constructions in shaping experiential meaning. By situating the analysis within the SFL paradigm, this work not only expands the descriptive grammar of Ekegusii but also demonstrates the theoretical relevance of SFL in analyzing under-described languages.

Keywords: Ekegusii, Systemic Functional Linguistics, Existential Processes, Declarative Clauses, Transitivity

Introduction

Over the past several decades, linguistics has increasingly shifted from a formalist emphasis on abstract syntactic rules to frameworks that foreground the relationship between language, meaning, and context. Among these paradigms, Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL), advanced by Halliday (1994) and further developed by Halliday and Matthiessen (2014), has provided a robust theoretical basis for exploring the interaction between

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grammatical structures and their communicative functions. Within this framework, language is conceptualized not merely as a set of grammatical rules but as a meaning-making resource deeply intertwined with its social, cultural, and cognitive contexts. One of the central pillars of SFL is the ideational metafunction, through which language is used to represent experiences and events. At the heart of this metafunction is the concept of transitivity—the system through which language encodes processes, participants, and circumstances within a clause.

Transitivity, in SFL, refers not to the traditional grammatical notion of transitive and intransitive verbs, but rather to how different kinds of processes (verbs) interact with their participants and circumstances in conveying experiential meaning. Halliday and Matthiessen (2014) classify these processes into six major types: material, mental, relational, behavioral, verbal, and existential. Each process type contributes distinctively to the construction of experiential meaning in discourse. The present study is concerned specifically with existential processes, which are those processes that express existence or the occurrence of entities, often through structures equivalent to “there is/are” in English. These processes are typically characterized by the presence of a single participant—the Existent—which is the entity whose presence is being asserted.

While existential processes have been well-documented in major world languages such as English, French, and Mandarin, their representation in African indigenous languages, including Bantu languages, remains under-researched. This study aims to fill this gap by focusing on how existential processes are grammatically realized in Ekegusii, an indigenous Bantu language spoken by the Abagusii people of Western Kenya. Ekegusii has received scholarly attention in terms of phonology (Cammenga, 2002), dialectology (Bosire, 1993), and syntax (Mecha, 2004), but its clause structures—particularly with regard to existential meaning—have not been systematically analyzed within the SFL framework.

Ekegusii presents a unique linguistic context for examining existential processes because of its morphological richness, agglutinative verb system, and distinct clause structure. The language is primarily spoken in Kisii and Nyamira counties in Kenya and comprises two main dialects: the Rogoro (Northern) and the Maate (Southern) dialects. For the purposes of this study, the Rogoro dialect has been chosen due to its relative standardization and widespread use in educational and religious texts. Understanding how existential meaning is expressed in this dialect provides a window into both the grammatical and cognitive patterns underlying Ekegusii communication. The central aim of this study is to investigate how existential processes are realized in Ekegusii declarative clauses, with a focus on polarity (affirmative vs. negative) and voice (active vs. passive). Declarative clauses are chosen for analysis because they are the most basic and unmarked form of clause structure, typically used to present factual information or assertions. In the context of existential meaning, such clauses serve to introduce new information about entities, states, or events into the discourse, making them a fertile site for transitivity analysis.

The conceptual framework of this study draws on the experiential metafunction of SFL, which considers language as a means of representing real-world experiences. In this perspective, the clause is treated as the basic unit of meaning, structured through configurations of processes, participants, and circumstances. For existential clauses in particular, the typical structure involves a verb that signals existence (e.g., “be” in English) and a nominal element that functions as the Existent. Circumstantial elements may also be present to specify location or time.

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In Ekegusii, these components are realized through morphologically complex verb forms and syntactic arrangements that are shaped by the language's agglutinative nature and Bantu typology.

The significance of analyzing existential processes in Ekegusii transcends mere grammatical description. It touches upon the broader issue of how indigenous languages encode and convey culturally embedded ways of thinking. Language is not a neutral medium; it reflects the cognitive and perceptual habits of its speakers. By examining how Ekegusii speakers express existential meaning, this study contributes to our understanding of how African worldviews and ontologies are linguistically instantiated. Moreover, given the increasing marginalization of indigenous languages in formal domains such as education, research of this nature helps document and preserve valuable linguistic knowledge that might otherwise be lost.

Furthermore, this study has practical implications for language teaching and translation. A clearer understanding of Ekegusii clause structures and their semantic underpinnings can inform the development of teaching materials for mother-tongue education, adult literacy programs, and bilingual curricula. It can also enhance the quality and accuracy of translations from and into Ekegusii, particularly in contexts where existential meaning is crucial—such as religious texts, public health materials, and legal documents.

Another area where the findings of this study could be impactful is computational linguistics and natural language processing (NLP). As NLP technologies begin to be developed for African languages, detailed linguistic descriptions such as the one provided in this study can serve as foundational resources for developing language models, parsers, and annotation tools tailored to Ekegusii. This could ultimately contribute to greater digital inclusion for Ekegusii speakers and increased representation of African languages in the global digital ecosystem. To achieve these objectives, the study analyzes data drawn from a combination of sources: religious texts (the Ekegusii Bible), educational materials (Ekegusii storybooks), and the researcher's native speaker intuition. These sources provide a rich corpus of naturally occurring language that reflects the everyday use of Ekegusii. By applying the analytical tools of SFL to this corpus, the study identifies the verbal patterns that realize existential processes, the syntactic roles of Existent participants, and the use of Circumstantial elements.

In sum, this research aims to contribute to three key domains: (1) theoretical linguistics, by extending the application of SFL to under-described languages; (2) language documentation, by providing a detailed account of existential meaning in Ekegusii; and (3) applied linguistics, by informing language teaching, translation, and technological development. Through a focused examination of existential processes within declarative clauses, the study not only sheds light on a specific grammatical phenomenon but also deepens our understanding of how language, thought, and culture are interconnected in the linguistic life of the Abagusii people. ExiPs are usually realised by the various forms of the verb 'to be' (such as *is*, *was*, *are* and *were*), which function as linking verbs that connect the Existent to the process of existence. Notably, ExiPs are usually introduced by two types of empty subjects (henceforth ES) - 'there' and 'it'. Whereas ExiPs that employ empty subjects, "there" introduce clauses that assert the existence of something, such as "There is a book on the table," the empty subject "It" introduces clauses that indicate the occurrence of an event or action, as in "It seems that the meeting was cancelled." It is worth mentioning that ExiP clauses may also include circumstantial elements whose role is to provide additional information regarding the existence or occurrence, typically expressed through prepositional or adverbial phrases (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014).

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Previous studies on transitivity include Sahabil's (2014) study on chapters of the English textbook Bahasa Inggris *When English Rings the Bell*, focusing on process types, participant functions, and circumstantial elements of transitivity that characterise English texts. The research discovered that relational processes were found to have the highest frequency of occurrence, followed by material, verbal, mental, existential and behavioural processes, respectively. Similarly, Darani (2014) evaluated and confirmed the realisation of persuasive style through existential and other processes in the literary text: 'Animal Farm,' by George Orwell (1945). On their part, Katawazai et al. (2021) evaluated processes in sports texts of the Postgraduate Students at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia" and established that material processes were the most frequently used, constituting approximately 53.40% of the total processes identified, with limited use of existential, behavioural, and verbal processes.

Regarding existential processes, Suherman (2018) investigated Ideational Metaphor in Political Texts from the perspective of Systemic Functional Linguistics and realised that though existential processes are one of the six processes commonly found in clauses, they are less frequently used in some contexts, as in the case of political texts, where material, mental, verbal and relational processes are prevalent and thus dominant. On the other hand, Afrianto and Inayati (2016) studied the use of existential processes in the novel *Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets*. Just like this study, Afrianto and Inayati confirmed that clauses realising existential processes consist of an empty subject signalled by the dummy 'there', one participant- the Existent, with the linking verb realising the process, and circumstances of place, and circumstances of time manner. From another perspective, Nhat (2021) studied existential processes in children's stories and established that existential processes are usually used to introduce characters at the very beginning of the stories.

Wakarindi (2010), looking at emphatic structures in Gikuyu, labels clauses indicating existence as existential structures and those indicating occurrence as occurrential structures. According to Wakarindi, these structures occur in both the affirmative and negative polarity, whereby whilst the affirmative existential structures indicate the existence of something, the negative structures indicate the non-existence of something. On the other hand, occurrential structures in Gikuyu are used to indicate that something occurred or will occur.

As far as Ekegusii is concerned, linguistic researchers have mainly focused on matters such as the consonantal processes in Ekegusii, drawing on theoretical assumptions and descriptive strategies of Natural Generative Grammar to show that phonological changes in the language result from different factors (Osinde, 1988); the nature of homonymous and polysemous Relations in Ekegusii, using the Sense Relations Theory (Aunga, 2011); the structure and role of the Determiner Phrase (DP) on Ekegusii using the Minimalist Programme (MP) (Mose, 2012); Forms of Politeness in Ekegusii, using Brown and Levinson's (1987) politeness Theory(Maisiba, 2015). Therefore, past studies on Ekegusii have largely ignored the realisation of existential processes in Ekegusii declarative clauses, which were the focus of this study.

Research Methodology

This research utilises a qualitative methodology that analyses transitivity within Ekegusii declarative clause, given that clauses are the foundational units in Systemic Functional Linguistics (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). The study sought to describe the manifestation of existential processes in Ekegusii. In this context, the study was conducted in the natural context without experimental intervention by utilising content analysis of existing written documents, which included selected Ekegusii storybooks, Ekegusii Bible, and the researcher's intuition. In

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particular, the study selected two storybooks: EmeganoYaito (Our Stories) by the National Centre for Early Childhood Education (henceforth NACECE) (1987); and Ninyanchete Omonwa Oito (I Like Our Language) by Ngoko (1979), and the Bible book - Ogokora kwa Abatomwa (Acts of the Apostles), from Ekegusii Bible, translated by The Bible Society of Kenya (1990). In this context, purposive sampling was used to gather data, including affirmative and negative Ekegusii declarative clauses expressing existence and occurrence. A total of six declarative clauses were selected and analysed thematically, categorised by their affirmative and negative forms, and further distinguished by their type as existential processes. This number of clauses was considered adequate for the study based on the awareness that a single text could generate large volumes of data after a linguistic analysis (Aberi, 2009).

Introspection was also employed to supplement the data where necessary, leveraging the researcher's native grammatical competence (Chomsky, 2015) in Ekegusii. The analysis aimed to fulfil the study's objectives by exploring the syntactic distinctions among various forms of Ekegusii declarative clauses. More significantly, an analysis of the transitivity of existential processes within the SFL framework established by Halliday and Matthiessen (2014) was conducted, with the clausal elements (ES, ExiP and Ex) being identified. Moreover, ExiPs were realised based on the polarity of the verbs in Ekegusii declaratives.

Results and Discussion

The study confirmed that existential processes indeed exist in Ekegusii clauses and are expressed through two types of verbs: those talking about the existence of something or not, such as '-o' (was), and '-aa' (is), and those talking about the occurrence/happening of something or not, such as '-beire' (is) and '-raba' (is). On the same note, it was discovered that Ekegusii verbs realising existential processes related to existence (such as '-o'(was), and '-aa'(is)) appear as suffixes which are attached to words denoting empty subjects (ES), such as Narengo (there) and Nare (there). Realised also, is the fact that existential clauses are usually introduced by two types of dummy/empty subjects (henceforth ES)- 'there' and 'it'. In this case, the ExiPs that talk about the existence or not are introduced by 'there' as in Narengo omonwa oyomo ore korokwa Nyoteyo (There was one person called Nyoteyo), whereby Narengo (There) is the ES; those that talk about something occurring or not are introduced by 'it' as in Bwabeire botuko gati (It is midnight), with Bwa (it) being the ES.

Evident also, was the fact that the ExiPs in Ekegusii occur in the two forms of polarity, affirmative and negative. Whilst the existential processes realised in the affirmative declaratives were found not to bear negative particles, as in Narengo omonwa oyomo ore korokwa Nyoteyo (There was one person called Nyoteyo), their negative counterparts bore negative markers (in the form of affixes such as 'ta-' (not) and 'ti-' (not), which are attached to the main verbs to signal negation. Examples include Monto ore buna Omonene Nyasae oito taiyo (There is no person who is like our Lord God) and Tichiraba chinsa inye (It is not ten o'clock). Notice that the negative signals are highlighted in bold.

Additionally, the data revealed that the negative ExiP clauses of occurrence have the negative particles embedded at the beginning of the ES, and the verb realizing the ExiP embedded at the end of the ES to form one word, which occupies the initial position of the clause followed by the Ex. This is seen in Tichiraba chinsa inye (It is not ten o'clock), in which Ti- (Not) is the negative marker, -chi- (it), is the ES, whereas chinsa inye (ten o'clock), is the Ex.

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Furthermore, it was revealed that ExiPs are never realised in either the active and passive forms in Ekegusii declaratives. This is due to the fact that the verbs representing ExiPs are the corpus type, (forms of the verb 'To Be' - such as is, was, are and were), whose role is to connect the elements of the clause in which they occur.

The study further confirmed that Ekegusii existential declaratives, whether affirmative or negative, containing ExiPs contain two obligatory elements: the participant, Existent (Ex), and the process (ExiP) attached to the empty subject (ES). In addition to the obligatory elements, Ekegusii existential declaratives contained Circumstances (Cirs), albeit optional. Besides, whereas the existential processes were found to be realised in both the affirmative and negative polarity in Ekegusii declaratives, they (ExiPs) are never realised in either the active or passive clause voice.

As discussed above, existential Processes (ExiPs) are usually realized by the various forms of the verb 'To Be', and are mostly introduced by two types of dummy/empty subjects (henceforth ES)- 'there' and 'it'. In this context, whereas the ExiPs that talk about the existence or not are introduced by 'there', those that talk about something happening or not are introduced by 'it'. Moreover, ExiP clauses comprise one participant, the Existent (henceforth Ex), realised by the nominal group, the process itself, Existential Process (henceforth ExiP), realised by the linking verb, and sometimes the Cirs.

As shown in the ensuing discussion, Ekegusii clauses tend to be realised by the two forms of verbs: those talking about the existence of something or not and those talking about something happening or not. In this regard, Ekegusii verbs used to represent ExiPs talking about the existence of something or not occur in the form of suffixes, such as '-o' (was), '-aa'(is), and '-iyo' (no), which are attached to the words representing the empty subjects (ES), such as; Narengo (there) and Nare (there).

On the basis of polarity, the study found that Exip clauses in the affirmative were found to have their grammatical subject positions occupied by the ES such as Narengo (there) and Nare (there), followed by the processes (ExiPs), such as '-o'(was) and '-aa'(is) which are in turn followed by Existents. This is illustrated by excerpts I and II below.

Excerpt I

Narengo omonto oyomo ore korokwa Nyoteyo (Ngoko, 1979) - Existence. There was person one called Nyoteyo

There was one person called Nyoteyo.

Narengo /-o / omonto oyomo ore korokwa Nyoteyo.

ES ExiP Ex

Excerpt II

Nareaa omonto oyomo omosibwa omosibwa otigetwe na Feliki. (Ekegusii Bible, 1990- Acts 25:14) - Existence.

Person one prison who was left by Felix

There is one prisoner who was left by Felix.

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Nare /aa / omosibwa oyomo omosibwa otigetwe na Feliki. ES
 ExiP Ex

These clauses are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Ekegusii Affirmative Existential Processes of Existence Clauses

No	ES	ExiP	Ex
I	Narenge There	-o was	omonto oyomo ore korokwa Nyoteyo one person called Nyoteyo
II	Nare There	-aa is	omonto oyomo omosibwa otigetwe na Feliki one prisoner who was left by Felix.

Conversely, the Ekegusii negative clauses realising existential processes were found to have their grammatical subject positions occupied by Existents. Moreover, the empty subjects (ESs) onto which the verbs representing the processes are embedded to form ES/ExiP were found to follow the Existents (Exs). This is evidenced in excerpts III and IV below, where Monto ore buna Omonene Nyasae oito (person who is like our Lord God), in excerpt III, and Mong’ina (old woman), in excerpt IV, are the Existents occupying the grammatical subject positions in the clauses.

Excerpt III

Monto ore buna Omonene Nyasae oito taiyo (Ekegusii Bible, 1990- Acts) - Existence.
 Person like Lord God our there is no.
 There is no person who is like our Lord God.

Monto ore buna Omonene Nyasae oito/taiyo.
 Ex ES/Exip

Excerpt IV

Mong’ina taiyo maate agwo (NACECE, 1987) - Existence.
 Old woman there is no down there.
 There is no old woman down there.

Mong’ina / taiyo / maate agwo.
 Ex ES/Exip Cir

These clauses are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Ekegusii Negative Existential Processes of Existence Clauses

No	Ex	ES/Exip	Cir
III	Monto ore buna Omonene Nyasae oito Person who is like our Lord	taiyo there is no	-

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IV	Mong'ina old woman	taiyo there is no	maate agwo down there
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On the contrary, the ExiP clauses talking about something occurring or not have their initial positions occupied by the empty subjects (ESs), followed by the verbs realising the processes (ExiPs), which are in turn followed by Existents (Exs). This is seen in excerpt V below, where Bwa- (It), is the ES, -beire (is), is the Exip, while botuko gati (midnight), is the Ex.

Excerpt V

Bwabeire botuko gati (Researcher's Intuition) - Occurrence. It has become night mid It is midnight.

Bwa/beire /botuko gati.

ES/Exip Ex

However, it is evident that the negative ExiP clauses of happening have the negative particle embedded at the beginning of the empty subject (ES), and the verb realising the process (ExiP) embedded at the end of the ES to form one word, which occupies the initial position of the clause followed by the Existent. This is seen in example VI below - Tichiraba chinsa inye (It is not ten o'clock), whereby Ti- (Not) is the negative particle, -chi- (it), is the ES, -raba (is), is the Exip, while chinsa inye (ten o'clock), is the Ex.

Excerpt VI

Tichiraba chinsa inye (Researcher's Intuition)- Occurrence.

Not it is ten o'clock

It is not ten o'clock.

Ti/chi/raba / chinsa inye

ES/Exip Ex

These analyses are illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3: Ekegusii Existential Processes of Occurrence Clauses

No.	Negative marker	ES	ExiP	Ex	Polarity
V	-	Bwa- It	- beire is	botuko gati midnight	Affirmative
VI	Ti- Not	-chi- it	- raba is	chinsa inye ten o'clock	Negative

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Most importantly, the data revealed that the verb types used in the realisation of existential processes Ekegusii declaratives, in both the affirmative and negative categories, are the copula/linking, whose role is to link the components in the clauses, the ES and the Ex, for that matter. In addition to the mandatory components (Existents and Processes), Ekegusii ExiP clauses were also found to contain Circumstances (Cirs), albeit optional, which complement the processes involved. *Maate agwo* (down there), in excerpt IV, is an example of a Circumstance identified in Ekegusii ExiP clauses.

Finally, it is worth noting that ExiPs are never realised in the active and passive forms in Ekegusii active declaratives. This is because the verbs used in the realisation of ExiPs are the linking type (forms of the verb 'To Be' - such as *is, was, are and were*), which do not imply any actions in the clauses, but rather connect the elements of the clause in which they occur.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the analysis of Ekegusii Existential Processes (ExiPs) reveals distinct structural patterns in both affirmative and negative clauses, highlighting the roles of empty subjects (ESs), processes (ExiPs), and Existents (Exs). Affirmative ExiPs consistently position the ES before the process and the Existent, as seen in examples I- *Narengo omonto oyomo ore korokwa Nyoteyo* (There was one person called Nyoteyo), while negative ExiPs invert this order, placing the Existent first, as demonstrated excerpt III- *Monto ore buna Omonene Nyasae oito taiyo* (There is no person who is like our Lord God) (see section 5). The study also identifies that ExiPs expressing occurrences follow a similar pattern, with the ES occupying the initial position, followed by the Existent. This is despite the fact that negative clauses incorporate a negative particle at the beginning of the clauses. Besides, the findings emphasise the use of linking verbs, forms of the verb 'be' (such as *is, was, are and were*) in these constructions (existential clauses), which serve to connect the various components of the clauses (ESs and Exs), while also noting that Ekegusii ExiPs do not manifest in active or passive forms due to the nature of the linking verbs employed.

Furthermore, the study confirmed that the transformations in Ekegusii's deep and surface structures, particularly the positioning of empty subjects, processes, and existents, significantly impact the functional purposes and contextual meanings when translated into English. For instance, the Ekegusii affirmative existential process, where the empty subject precedes the process and the existent, translates into a straightforward English sentence like "There was one person called Nyoteyo." Conversely, the negative existential process, with the existent followed by the empty subject/process combination, requires a more complex English translation, such as "There is no person who is like our Lord God." These transformations highlight the distinct ways Ekegusii conceptualises existence, which can be challenging to convey in English directly. Understanding these structural differences is crucial for accurate and culturally sensitive translations, preserving the nuances of Ekegusii thought and expression. Overall, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of Ekegusii's syntactic structures and realisation of existential processes.

This study makes significant contributions to the understanding of Ekegusii language and its speakers' conceptualisation of existence. By linking transitivity to existential thought, the study reveals how the grammatical structures of Ekegusii reflect the speakers' perceptions of existence and relationships between entities, an interplay that has been largely overlooked in previous studies. Furthermore, the findings demonstrate

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distinct syntactic patterns in Ekegusii ExiPs, particularly the consistent positioning of empty subjects (ESs), processes (ExiPs), and existents (Exs) in both affirmative and negative clauses. This structural analysis contributes to a more nuanced understanding of the realisation of existential processes in Ekegusii declarative clauses. More significantly, the study elucidates how Indigenous languages like Ekegusii can provide unique insights into human thought and perception, thereby demonstrating the usefulness of Halliday and Mathiessen's (2014) theory of SFL as a methodological framework for analysing language in context.

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